

FORMATION OF STUDENTS' IMAGE LITERACY

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Abstract. *The article is written about the nationality of fine art and the importance of design art, photo art, and practical skills of Ikebana compositions in students' artistic perception of art.*

Keywords: *fine art, reader, design art, Ikebana composition, photo art, fine art, composition.*

ФОРМИРОВАНИЕ ИМИДЖЕВОЙ ГРАМОТНОСТИ СТУДЕНТОВ

Аннотация. *В статье говорится о национальности изобразительного искусства и значении дизайнерского искусства, фотоискусства, практических навыков составления икебанных композиций в художественном восприятии учащимися искусства.*

Ключевые слова: *изобразительное искусство, читатель, дизайнерское искусство, икебанный композиция, фотоискусство, изобразительное искусство, композиция.*

INTRODUCTION

Drawing develops not only the speed of visual perception, but also a good visual memory. Art is the expression of events in nature and society in artistic images. In addition to reflecting the general state and development of the material world, and being an important tool for communicating it to people, art serves as a powerful factor in educating people politically, morally, and artistically. The subject of visual art serves to develop visual literacy in students, creative thinking in the process of mastering other subjects, acquiring knowledge necessary in social life by developing artistic-aesthetic thinking and emotional sensitivity during the lesson. Art is divided into such types as visual arts, architecture, literature, music, circus, theater, cinema, radio and television, according to the way of expressing reality, character, and content. The positive and most important feature of art is that, unlike science, it expresses events not in concepts, but in forms perceived by intuition and feeling, in typical artistic images.

It is known that each society creates certain conditions for the development of art based on its economic and political situation. Therefore, the art of each society serves its time. If the art of every society is created on the basis of freedom, this art promotes the advanced idea of humanity, patriotism and nationalism. Art reflects people's goals and hopes.

METHOD AND METHODOLOGY

Art fully expresses the good intentions of mankind, their dreams and hopes. Therefore, as much as our nation respects and respects its art, the nations of the world look at Uzbek art with the same sincerity and respect. Based on these requirements and principles, Uzbek artists in their works reflect the things and events that interest them and excite them on the basis of nationality.

The nationalism of the visual art of our independent country requires it, first of all, to stand in a realistic position and depict the objective laws of the material world. This requires the artist to express things and events clearly, like himself, realistically, and to create works of art that are directed towards a specific goal and meet high artistic requirements. World realistic

visual art is a real mirror that represents the past, present and future life of peoples of the world, as well as nature and society. We see the past, present and future in it. For this reason, masters of realistic visual arts should know the history of the past, matter and development, mathematics, nature, geography and biology. Art has a long history, it was formed on the basis of the development and improvement of labor activity in society and the progress of social activity.

Development of the skills of perception of an artistic image is the basis of learning works of art. Pupils should be able to think and perceive the work, to express its content using special expressions, and also to notice and emphasize the visual means used in the work. Special hours are not allocated to the perception of art in elementary grades. It is carried out in the classes of painting composition, drawing according to nature. Educational materials on the perception of works of visual art in primary grades are related to the practical work of students. Fine art - helps to facilitate easy, short and reasonable teaching of all academic subjects taught at school and has long been recognized as a science that creates conditions for the implementation of all types of education, both theoretically and practically. will be done. [1; 47]

RESEARCH RESULTS

Showing copies of works of art and talking about them increases children's interest in art and leads them to work in this field. During the presentation of the works, children are introduced to the main idea expressed in it and the artistic and visual tools used. The importance of design art in the perception of an artistic image.

Design art consists of applied, artistic and graphic arts. This art mainly serves technology and its development. Therefore, it is also called "industrial aesthetics" or "technical art". It is known that technology is an important factor in easing people's work and creating comfortable opportunities for them. [2;33]

The simplicity, convenience and beauty of the technique improves the working conditions of the worker and improves his mood. Therefore, the creation of new forms and types of tools, household items, technical tools, plays an important role in managing the economy and material and spiritual life of society. It is known that all generation of industrial products, starting from household goods, material and spiritual goods, labor tools, transport, equipment, means of production and mechanization. Because all of them are made in factories, workshops and shops.

Design art is one of the newest types of fine art, which consists of artist-constructor art. This science of art mainly studies issues such as the theoretical basis of industrial art design, the laws of its socio-economic and historical development, as well as the principles and methods of art design, the creative activities of designer artists. The art of design consists of the art of general and artistic design, which creates new types of machines, technical tools, building facades, walls, hand tools, household items, clothes. The art of design carries out this creation by juxtaposing human labor and beauty. In its place, it teaches people to live comfortably, comfortably, to work effectively, and educates them with high taste, love for work, spiritual culture, and high passion for the beauty of nature and society.

DISCUSSION

Photo art. Photography. The art of photography is the art of expressing reality clearly, as it is (in nature), without any additions, using scientific and technical tools. [2;34]

In recent years, due to the high development of photography techniques and the creativity and skills of the representatives of this field, the works of photography attract people's attention.

The art of photography can be considered a type of fine art. Because this art also satisfies certain needs of people. The art of photography, like fine art, has its own types and genres. He has portrait, landscape, life, and historical genres. Despite the fact that the art of photography has been developed since the 1930s, today it is an effective tool in film, television, book printing, newspaper and magazine publishing, in studying our ancient history and finding lost traces, in creating our present history.

The art of Ikebana. Ikebana is a type of fine art, which means "artistic arrangement of living flowers" in Japanese. The art of Ikebana gives people a positive mental mood. It educates humanity in the spirit of love for existence, nature, work. It develops people's aesthetic and artistic taste, inspires work and creativity.[2;35]

The art of Ikebana differs from other arts in terms of its structure and content, and it is closer to the art of sculpture. Because it is possible to see and watch this composition of art not from one side, but from all sides. The art of Ikebana brings people to places of residence (such as rooms, hotels, shared dormitories), rooms of educational and scientific institutions (children's institutions, classrooms of schools, auditoriums, scientific laboratories, offices, department rooms), work and workplaces (It is the most convenient and lively, educational art tool widely used in the decoration of factories, workshops, their halls and corridors), cultural institutions, health care institutions and rest houses, cinema theaters, etc. This art is not only a means of decoration, but according to the Japanese definition, it is to build or create a small part of nature with the high skill of a skilled artist at any place, at any time, under any conditions. Ikebana is made in different styles, using different materials, depending on the place or object of use.

Ikebana composition consists of three elements - flower, leaf, branch, and the three positions of these elements express the wholeness, integrity, meaning and beauty of the composition. The first of the elements of the composition is the longest, high-volume branch in the composition, which expresses the content and character of the entire composition; the second is a medium-length branch or flower (leaf) in the composition, which provides unity of color and proportion while filling the content of the composition; the third is the smallest among the elements, and it is an auxiliary element in ensuring color harmony by equalizing the theme, character, content, color and proportions of the composition. The composition of Ikebana, pleasant and beautiful, depends on the correct choice of colors, the shape, color and material of the container chosen for the composition, as well as how well it is adapted to the place and object of the composition.

CONCLUSION

Special dishes made of porcelain, crystal, glass, ceramics, plastic, metal, and wood are used for Ikebana. These dishes consist of tall vases, low plates, plates, and basket-shaped dishes. Although the art of Ikebana was formed in Japan 600 years ago, and there are about 60 types and styles of it, its representatives such as Ikenoba, Nageira, Moribana, Ohara, Sogesu created a school with its own style and direction. contributed to the development of this art. Today, when the art of Ikebana is gradually entering the art of the peoples of the world, another new type of this art - the art of Akobana - has appeared in Japan. This art feature consists in creating an artistic composition in a special frame based on the processing of dried flowers, leaves, twigs, fruits, animals and other natural materials.

Fine art works invite people to philosophical observations and serve as the backbone of our spirituality. Fine art educational subject has a wide opportunity to form and develop aesthetic

taste, artistic thinking, intellectual potential, and most importantly, general worldview in the young generation.

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